

VARIABLE	FHIR ELEMENT	LOINC	SNOMED	UNIT OF MEASURE	SHORT DESCRIPTION	TYPE
ID	Patient.identifier	-	-	—	Unique patient identifier	string
Sex	Patient.gender	LOINC: 46098-0	-	—	Values: male, female, other, unknown	string
Age	Patient.birthDate	LOINC: 21611-9	-	years (a)	Age derived from date of birth	numeric
WHO 2016 MDS Classification	Condition.code	-	SNOMED:109995007	—	MDS classification according to WHO 2016	string
Leukocytes x10 ⁶ /uL	Observation.code	-	SNOMED:277288007	10 ⁶ /μL	White blood cell count	numeric
Neutrophils x10 ⁶ /uL	Observation.code	-	SNOMED:1022551000000104	10 ⁶ /μL	Neutrophil count	numeric
Monocytes x10 ⁶ /uL	Observation.code	-	SNOMED:1107991000000100	10 ⁶ /μL	Monocyte count	numeric
Hemoglobin g/L	Observation.code	-	SNOMED:38082009	g/L	Hemoglobin concentration	numeric
Platelets x10 ⁶ /uL	Observation.code	-	SNOMED:365632008	10 ⁶ /μL	Platelet count	numeric
% bone marrow blasts	Observation.code	LOINC: 55433-7	-	%	Percentage of bone marrow blasts	numeric
% bone marrow ring sideroblasts	Observation.code	-	-	%	Percentage of ring sideroblasts in bone marrow	numeric
Multilineage dysplasia (yes/no)	Observation.code	-	SNOMED:2572300	boolean	Presence of multilineage dysplasia	string
Bone marrow fibrosis (yes/no)	Observation.code	-	SNOMED:52967002	boolean	Presence of bone marrow fibrosis	string
Karyotype (ISCN formula)	Observation.code	LOINC: 62356-1	-	text	ISCN karyotype formula	string
IPSS risk group	Observation.code	-	-	category	IPSS risk group	string
IPSSR risk group	Observation.code	-	-	category	IPSS-R risk group	string
Comorbidity score index	Observation.code	LOINC: 96750-5	-	score	Comorbidity index (e.g., Charlson)	string
AML Evolution	Condition.code	-	-	boolean	Evolution to acute myeloid leukemia (AML)	string
Time to AML (days)	Observation.valueQuantity	-	-	days	Interval to AML onset	numeric
Status at last follow-up	Observation.code	-	-	status (text/code)	Status (alive, deceased, etc.)	string
Time to last follow-up (days)	Observation.valueQuantity	-	-	days	Time to last follow-up	numeric

CLASSIFICATION_SOURCE	ENTRY_TYPE	HGN_CID	OMIM	ENTREZ_GENE_ID	ENSEMBL_ID	GENE_SYMBOL	VARIABLE_ANNOTATION	SHORT_DESCRIPTION	ANNOTATION
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:18318	612990	171023	ENSG00000171456	ASXL1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Polycomb group protein ASXL1	Probable Polycomb group (PcG) protein involved in ...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:886	300032	546	ENSG00000085224	ATRX	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Transcriptional regulator ATRX	Involved in transcriptional regulation and chromat...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:20893	300485	54880	ENSG00000183337	BCOR	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	BCL-6 corepressor	Transcriptional corepressor. May specifically inhi...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:25657	300688	63035	ENSG00000085185	BCORL1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	BCL-6 corepressor-like protein 1	Transcriptional corepressor. May specifically inhi...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:1097	164757	673	ENSG00000157764	BRAF	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Serine/threonine-protein kinase B-raf	Protein kinase involved in the transduction of mit...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:1541	109091	811	ENSG00000179218	CALR	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Calreticulin	Calcium-binding chaperone that promotes folding, o...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:1542	165360	867	ENSG00000110395	CBL	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase CBL	Adapter protein that functions as a negative regul...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:1833	604491	868	ENSG00000114423	CBLB	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase CBL-B	E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase which accepts ubiquiti...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:1833	116897	1050	ENSG00000245848	CEBPA	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein alpha	Transcription factor that coordinates proliferatio...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:2439	138971	1441	ENSG00000119535	CSF3R	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Granulocyte colony-stimulating factor receptor	Receptor for granulocyte colony-stimulating factor...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:2978	602769	1788	ENSG00000119772	DNMT3A	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	DNA (cytosine-5)-methyltransferase 3A	Required for genome-wide de novo methylation and i...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:3495	600618	2120	ENSG00000139083	ETV6	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Transcription factor ETV6	Transcriptional repressor...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:3527	601573	2146	ENSG00000106462	EZH2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase EZH2	Polycomb group (PcG) protein. Catalytic subunit of...

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HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:16712	606278	55294	ENSG00000109670	FBXW7	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	F-box/WD repeat-containing protein 7	Substrate recognition component of a SCF (SKP1-CUL...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:3765	136351	2322	ENSG00000122025	FLT3	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Receptor-type tyrosine-protein kinase FLT3	Tyrosine-protein kinase that acts as cell-surface ...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:4171	137295	2624	ENSG00000179348	GATA2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Endothelial transcription factor GATA-2	Transcriptional activator which regulates endothel...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:4392	139320	2778	ENSG00000087460	GNAS	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(s) subunit alpha isoforms XLas	Guanine nucleotide-binding proteins (G proteins) f...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:4396	139380	2782	ENSG00000078369	GNB1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Guanine nucleotide-binding protein G(I)/G(S)/G(T) subunit beta-1	Guanine nucleotide-binding proteins (G proteins) a...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:5382	147700	3417	ENSG00000138413	IDH1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Isocitrate dehydrogenase 1.	...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:5383	147650	3418	ENSG00000182054	IDH2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Isocitrate dehydrogenase [NADP], mitochondrial	Plays a role in intermediary metabolism and energy...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:6192	147796	3717	ENSG00000096968	JAK2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Tyrosine-protein kinase JAK2	Non-receptor tyrosine kinase involved in various p...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:6342	164920	3815	ENSG00000157404	KIT	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Mast/stem cell growth factor receptor Kit	Tyrosine-protein kinase that acts as cell-surface ...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:6407	190070	3845	ENSG00000133703	KRAS	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	GTPase KRas, N-terminally processed	Ras proteins bind GDP/GTP and possess intrinsic GT...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:7217	159530	4352	ENSG00000117400	MPL	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Thrombopoietin receptor	Receptor for thrombopoietin that acts as a primary...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:3495	600618	2120	ENSG00000139083	ETV6	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Transcription factor ETV6	Transcriptional repressor...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/Ensembl_ID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:3527	601573	2146	ENSG00000106462	EZH2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Histone-lysine N-methyltransferase EZH2	Polycomb group (PcG) protein. Catalytic subunit of...

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HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:7765	613113	4763	ENSG00000196712	NF1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Neurofibromin truncated	Stimulates the GTPase activity of Ras. NF1 shows g...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:7881	190198	4851	ENSG00000148400	NOTCH1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Neurogenic locus notch homolog protein 1	Functions as a receptor for membrane-bound ligands...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:7910	164040	4869	ENSG00000181163	NPM1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Nucleophosmin	Involved in diverse cellular processes such as rib...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:7989	164790	4893	ENSG00000213281	NRAS	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	GTPase NRas	Ras proteins bind GDP/GTP and possess intrinsic GT...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:18145	300414	84295	ENSG00000156531	PHF6	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	PHD finger protein 6	Transcriptional regulator that associates with rib...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:8957	311770	5277	ENSG00000165195	PIGA	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Phosphatidylinositol N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase subunit A	Necessary for the synthesis of N-acetylglucosami...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:9277	605100	8493	ENSG00000170836	PPM1D	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Protein phosphatase 1D	Involved in the negative regulation of p53 express...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:25031	621019	25766	ENSG00000110844	PRPF40B	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Pre-mRNA-processing factor 40 homolog B	May be involved in pre-mRNA splicing....
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:9644	176876	5781	ENSG00000179295	PTPN11	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type 11	Acts downstream of various receptor and cytoplasmic...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:9811	606462	5885	ENSG00000164754	RAD21	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Double-strand-break repair protein rad21 homolog	[Double-strand-break repair protein rad21 homolog]...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:10471	151385	861	ENSG00000159216	RUNX1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Runt-related transcription factor 1	Forms the heterodimeric complex core-binding facto...

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HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:15573	611060	26040	ENSG00000152217	SETBP1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	SET binding protein 1.	...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:10768	605590	23451	ENSG00000115524	SF3B1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Splicing factor 3B subunit 1	Involved in pre-mRNA splicing as a component of th...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:11111	300040	8243	ENSG00000072501	SMC1A	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Structural maintenance of chromosomes protein 1A	Involved in chromosome cohesion during cell cycle ...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:12468	606062	9126	ENSG00000108055	SMC3	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Structural maintenance of chromosomes protein 3	Central component of cohesin, a complex required f...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:10783	600813	6427	ENSG00000161547	SRSF2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Serine/arginine-rich splicing factor 2	Necessary for the splicing of pre-mRNA. It is requ...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:11355	300826	10735	ENSG00000101972	STAG2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Cohesin subunit SA-2	Component of cohesin complex, a complex required f...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:125941	612839	54790	ENSG00000168769	TET2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Methylcytosine dioxygenase TET2	Dioxygenase that catalyzes the conversion of the m...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:11998	191170	7157	ENSG00000141510	TP53	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Cellular tumor antigen p53	Acts as a tumor suppressor in many tumor types...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:12453	191317	7307	ENSG00000160201	U2AF1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Splicing factor U2AF 35 kDa subunit	Plays a critical role in both constitutive and enh...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	-	607102	7490	ENSG00000184937	UTX	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Lysine-specific demethylase 6A	Histone demethylase that specifically demethylates...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:12796	607899	51352	ENSG00000183242	WT1	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	Wilms tumor protein	Transcription factor that plays an important role ...
HGNC/OMIM/EntrezGeneID/EnsemblID/Gene_symbol	gene	HGNC:123019	300028	8233	ENSG00000169249	ZRSR2	0 = wildtype; 1 = mutated	U2 small nuclear ribonucleoprotein auxiliary factor 35 kDa subunit-related protein 2	Pre-mRNA-binding protein required for splicing of ...